

School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences

**“The effect of Social Power Motives on Collective Action for Women’s
Rights”**

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Abstract:

We evaluated the effects of three social power motives- desire for dominance, prestige and leadership (DoPL)- on protective and feminist collective action for gender equality with the aim to uncover how leading and power-motivated figures behave in regards to gender equality. Feminist action is linked to real progress, whereas protective action maintains the current structure of the social hierarchy. Participants rated their agreement with numerous statements regarding their willingness to engage in collective action, as well as their level of desire for the three power motives in an online survey. Various relevant attitudes, such as benevolent and hostile sexism, sex, feminist identity and social dominance orientation were controlled for in the survey. Multilevel multivariate multiple regression modelling under a Bayesian framework indicated that desire for leadership and prestige trigger a willingness to engage in feminist action, while individuals who desire dominance oppose said action. In addition, we failed to present evidence that any of the three motives predicts protective action. Findings suggest that the motive of dominance obstructs gender equality from progressing, while leadership- and prestige-oriented individuals support movements that confront the current social hierarchy. Future studies are encouraged to replicate our findings in the field.

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No aspect of well-being is more fundamental than freedom from personal harm motivated by hatred or fear of one's ascribed characteristics, that is, freedom from ideologically justified violence against one's person. Without such freedom it is impossible to implement other choices. To the extent that women's personal freedom is still restricted and denied, we can continue to speak of oppression.

—Sheffield (1987, p. 171)

Introduction:

Despite recent advances in the fight for gender equality, significant barriers and cases of discrimination, including overt violence, remain alarmingly common. Women are at a greater risk of sexual terrorism induced by men, either through actual or implied violence whose purpose is to maintain the patriarchal social order, while a proper response from the state is lacking (Sheffield, 1987). Reported rape offences were up to 70,330 in the year ending March 2022, from which only 3.16% of cases were brought to trial (ONS, 2022). Moreover, women come across unequal access to opportunities for their advancement and achievement, and are differentially rewarded for equal work. According to the Department of International Trade, the hourly mean difference in average pay between men and women was 5.8% (2022). Although there has been a slow decline of the gender pay gap over time, the multiple times gender-based activism was faced with stalling, backlash and even reversion of any advances do not allow for feelings of reassurance.

There are at least two types of collective action in response to gender inequality: feminist and protective action (Radke, Hornsey & Barlow, 2018). Women that fight for gender equality participate in both protective and feminist action, whereas men are more probable to engage in protective action (Radke, et al, 2018). Protective action aims to protect women from gender violence and equips them with training, tools and tactics, as a way to deal with the consequences of the current status quo. On the other hand, feminist action targets the cause of

gender inequality and is associated to real progress. Women's greater willingness to take part in feminist action and gender-based activism is a product of their enhanced feminist consciousness (Radke et al, 2018; Siegel, Elbe & Calogero, 2022). Radke, Kutlaca, Siem, Wright and Becker (2020) built on the extended social identity model of collective action (extended SIMCA; Van Zomeren, Kutlaca & Turner-Zwinkels, 2018) with the aim to explain why men, a comparatively advantaged group, are motivated to engage in action for women.

Subsequently, four categories of motivations were identified: outgroup-focused motives, which involve a true interest in bettering the status of a disadvantaged group, ingroup-focused motivations, which entail support for a lower status group only when the status quo is maintained in their favour, personal motivations, that reflect one's engagement in action for improving the status of a disadvantaged group, depending on whether this would meet their own personal needs and finally, morality motivations, which entail the incitement of collective action according to moral beliefs (Radke et al, 2020). Men who are outgroup-focused are true allies to women and will engage in any type of collective action, either feminist or protective, to improve their status. On the contrary, ingroup-focused men will engage in action that does not threaten their higher status, such as participating in a protest against sexual violence, but not sign petitions for equal pay and access to opportunities in the workplace.

The framework proposed by Radke and colleagues (2020) does not consider social power as a motive for collective action. Desire for power is an essential component in the fight for social equality and is relevant to the four outlined motivations, as well as the behavioural outcomes associated with them. Suessenbach, Loughnan, Schönbrodt and Moore (2019) proposed a taxonomy of social power motives with the aim to predict impactful behaviour. Power motives were differentiated according to the two social hierarchies of dominance and prestige, as well as a third distinct motive, desire for leadership (DoPL). Hierarchy exists in most human social groups for the actions of their members to be coordinated in a way that is

deemed beneficial for the group (Maner & Case, 2016). Individuals are motivated to achieve a high status within hierarchically organized groups, because of the respect, the ability to live comfortably and access to resources this status offers. All three social power motives are considered explicit and are related to distinct attributes, which aim at the attainment of influence on the attitudes, emotions and behaviours of others, and consequently at the ascendance to positions of high rank (Suessenbach & Moore, 2015). Power motives are thought to mediate the relationship between beliefs and behaviours (Higgins & Kruglanski, 2000). They are the driving force that makes change possible or obstructs progress, depending on whether the current structure of the social hierarchy is beneficial or detrimental.

Dominance involves the coercion of a group member into adhering another member's will. Desire for dominance is an evolutionary-driven behaviour observed in both males and females with males exhibiting stronger motivation and more extreme forms of aggression and risk taking (Suessenbach et al, 2019). According to Dworkin (1985) dominance is a social or political dynamic, which involves hierarchy, objectification, submission and violence. A high rank in the dominance hierarchy is not freely conferred, but rather seized through intimidation, fear, coercion and manipulation strategies (Maner, 2017). A manipulation strategy was introduced by Shnabel, Bar-Anan, Kende, Bareket and Lazar (2016), who proposed that certain types of helping behaviours can be adopted by men, as a way to promote dependency and minimise the autonomy of women. This is in line with Bischof's study (2008), which demonstrated that prosocial behaviour can be used as a mean to increase dominance by binding another person to oneself. Dominance driven individuals in leadership positions favour the maintenance of their power over the wellbeing of their group (Maner & & Mead) and tend to be negatively associated with prosocial behaviour (Suessenbach et al, 2019),

Prestige involves the search for admiration, respect, greater interpersonal influence and access to resources, through claiming greater prosocial behaviour. To achieve this, helping

behaviours are usually demonstrated in public (Radke et al, 2020), as well as the display of valued skills, abilities, and accomplishments. According to Suessenbach and colleagues (2019) desire for prestige is moderately related to claiming moral standards, although it was found to be weakly exhibited through prosocial actions. This finding suggests that once the moral standards of an individual seeking prestige are endorsed, they cease to behave altruistically. This might explain why the abolishment of gender inequalities has yet to be achieved, despite the support women seemingly receive. For instance, popular movements for women's rights, such as the #MeToo movement, favour short-term visibility over long-term change, which offers individuals the opportunity to demonstrate prosocial behaviour, but not abide by it. On the other hand, fear of losing power and reputation can trigger efforts of higher-prestige ranked individuals to maintain their status (Maner & Case, 2016). Power and reputation are very easy to lose, especially when the hierarchy of a social group becomes unstable and higher status individuals might not wish for their position to be at risk for not taking action.

Both prestige and dominance have been previously investigated as explicit social power motives, but leadership has only recently been distinguished as an alternative source of social power attainment. It has been proposed that the desire to lead, as well as the possession of leader-specific attributes has the capacity to maximise one's position in both prestige and leadership hierarchies (Maner, 2017). Moreover, evolutionary approaches assume that leadership and followership have coevolved during the emergence of coordination problems in social groups throughout human history (Van Vugt, 2006). Taking on such roles is favoured by natural selection, because joint effort would be more advantageous for the group than uncoordinated action. Having leadership skills involves the initiative to lead a group toward a common goal and taking responsibility (Suessenbach et al, 2019). Leadership-driven individuals are responsible for the establishment of goals, logistics of coordination, effort monitoring, dispute resolution, rewards and punishment (Glowacki & von Rueden, 2015).

Helping behaviours can be adopted by leading figures, as a way to demonstrate responsibility (Van Vungt, 2006).

Current study:

Our aim is to examine the effect of social power motives on the likelihood of participating in action for gender equality, because real progress will be made only when the rights of women are prioritized over the maintenance of the “status quo” and the overall public opinion is shifted (Subašić, Reynolds & Turner, 2008). This study is a multi-national replication project and extension of previous work. Thus, in a Bayesian framework, our predictions take the form of priors, which are obtained from the posterior estimates of a previous UK sample (<https://osf.io/3zb6m>). We express our predictions as priors for standardized regression coefficients (Bs), zero-order correlation coefficients (Rs) and 95% highest density intervals on those estimates (95% HDIs).

Firstly, we hypothesize that both the desire for leadership and prestige will predict one’s willingness to engage in feminist action ($\beta_{LFA} = 0.09$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.16], $\beta_{PFA} = 0.16$, 95% HDI = [0.08, 0.23]). On the other hand, dominance as a social power motive is expected to predict opposition to taking feminist action ($\beta_{DFA} = -0.14$, 95% HDI = [-0.22, -0.07]). Protecting women from gender violence is believed to be predicted by desire for prestige ($\beta_{PPA} = 0.16$, 95% HDI = [0.06, 0.25]), whereas dominance is considered an indicator of low support ($\beta_{DPA} = -0.14$, 95% HDI = [-0.23, -0.04]). Although, there were no substantive predictions from previous work for desire for leadership, this motive is expected to be an indicator of protective action ($\beta_{LPA} = -0.04$, 95% HDI = [-0.15, 0.06]).

We acknowledge that certain attitudes, them being feminist identity (FI), social dominance orientation (SDO; Pratto, Sidanius, Stallworth & Malle, 1994), gender, benevolent and hostile sexism, are relevant to the willingness to engage in collective action for women’s

rights, as well as to the DoPL components. Therefore, to test the unique predictive power of DoPL, we will control for these attitudes in the study. SDO, as a measure of acceptance of inequality ($b_{SDOFA} = -0.36$, 95% HDI = [-0.44, -0.27]), as well as hostile sexism ($b_{HostSexismFA} = -0.28$, 95% HDI = [-0.37, -0.19]) will both negatively predict feminist and protective action ($b_{SDOPA} = -0.14$, 95% HDI = [-0.24, -0.02], $b_{HostSexismPA} = -0.17$, 95% HDI = [-0.28, -0.06]). On the contrary, identifying as a female ($b_{SexFA} = 0.21$, 95% HDI = [0.09, 0.33]), holding beliefs that coincide with benevolent sexism ($b_{BenSexismFA} = 0.20$, 95% HDI = [0.12, 0.27]) and considering oneself to be a feminist ($b_{FeminismFA} = 0.28$, 95% HDI = [0.20, 0.36]) are hypothesized to predict one's involvement in the fight for women's rights. These individual differences are also expected to predict involvement in collective action with the aim to protect women from the consequences of the current status quo ($b_{SexPA} = 0.34$, 95% HDI = [0.14, 0.54], $b_{BenSexismPA} = 0.38$, 95% HDI = [0.29, 0.48], $b_{FeminismPA} = 0.19$, 95% HDI = [0.08, 0.31]).

Protective action is expected to be negatively correlated with age ($r_{AgePA} = -0.11$, 95% HDI = [-0.21, 0.0]), as well as hostile sexism ($r_{HostSexismPA} = -0.14$, 95% HDI = [-0.24, -0.04]) and SDO ($r_{SDOPA} = -0.20$, 95% HDI = [-0.30, -0.10]). Furthermore, we predict that feminist identity ($r_{FIPA} = 0.33$, 95% HDI = [0.23, 0.42]) and benevolent sexism ($r_{BenSexismPA} = 0.19$, 95% HDI = [0.09, 0.29]) will have a positive relationship with one's involvement in collective action for the purpose of protecting women. Feminist action is predicted to be positively associated with the desire for prestige ($r_{PFA} = 0.17$, 95% HDI = [0.07, 0.27]) and leadership ($r_{LFA} = 0.12$, 95% HDI = [0.02, 0.22]) and negatively correlated with SDO ($r_{SDOFA} = -0.61$, 95% HDI = [-0.67, -0.55]), as well as both types of sexism ($r_{HostSexismFA} = -0.54$, 95% HDI = [-0.61, -0.47], $r_{BenSexismFA} = -0.09$, 95% HDI = [-0.20, 0.00]). Finally, willingness to engage in both feminist and protective action for gender equality are predicted to have a positive moderate correlation ($r_{FAPA} = 0.42$, 95% HDI = [0.34, 0.50]).

Methods:**Participants:**

The final sample size consisted of 241 participants (120, 49.8% women, 121 men) who were tested online via Qualtrics and recruited from Prolific Academic (<https://www.prolific.co/>). They were either located in the United States or the United Kingdom and were not allowed to participate more than once. Subjects were paid £2.35GBP for their participation in the study. Their ages ranged between 18 to 70 years-old with a mean age of 33.72 (SD= 12.05). Three participants identified as non-binary and were removed from subsequent analyses, since effects could not be reliably estimated with three observations. Another ten participants were removed from the analysis, as they did not complete all items in the survey.

Design:

We tested our hypotheses in a within-subjects design implemented in two different samples (UK sample, US sample). The independent variables of the study are the DoPL social power motives. Furthermore, individual differences, them being hostile and benevolent sexism, SDO, feminist identity and gender are hypothesised to predict participants' intention to engage in collective action for gender equality and thus, were controlled for. The depended variables of the study are protective and feminist action.

Materials:

All materials can be found in Appendix B and on OSF (<https://osf.io/3zb6m>). Feminist and protective action were measured with a seven-item scale obtained by Radke and colleagues (2018). Both the feminist ($\alpha= 0.84$) and protective ($\alpha= 0.81$) action questionnaires, which consisted of four (e.g. "I would be willing to protest against sexism.") and three items (e.g. "I would be willing to sponsor women to attend a self-defence class to learn how to protect themselves.") respectively, are considered reliable scales. Two items from the protective action

questionnaire were alternated for the UK sample, as the original version was deemed unsuitable regarding United Kingdom’s current legal system (see Table 1).

Table 1: Protective Action Questionnaire for US and UK sample (Radke et al, 2018).

US version	UK version (modified)
“I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can obtain a gun license and firearm to protect themselves.”	“I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can be given and trained to use a legal 3-inch folding blade to protect themselves.”
“I would be willing to sponsor women to attend a self-defence class to learn how to protect themselves.”	
“I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can be given and trained to use a Taser to protect themselves.”	“I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can obtain and be trained to use a legal defense spray to protect themselves.”

Although, the protective questionnaire was adapted for the UK sample, the reason why women need to be sponsored- which is to protect themselves from gender-based violence- remains clearly stated. Participants disclosed their willingness to engage in collective action for women’s rights on a seven-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 7= Strongly Agree) with the midpoint signalling neutrality. Items for protective action were summed, as well as items for feminist action, with higher scores signifying a greater intent to participate in protective and feminist collective action.

Desire for dominance ($\alpha = 0.78$), prestige ($\alpha = 0.81$) and leadership ($\alpha = 0.88$) as social power motives for action on behalf of women’s rights were measured with the use of a 12-item questionnaire retrieved from Suessenbach and colleagues (2019). The questionnaire consists of four items for each of the three DoPL motives. Participants indicated their level of agreement with ten statements (e.g. “I relish opportunities in which I can lead others.”) on a six-point Likert scale that did not include a neutral response (1= Strongly Disagree, 6= Strongly Agree). There were, also, two motive-oriented goals (e.g. “Be respected and admired by other people.”), for which subjects rated their importance on a six-point scale (1= Not important to me, 6= Extremely important to me). The higher an individual scores for each motive, the more driven they are considered to be by said motive.

The Achievement and Affiliation Motive questionnaire derived by Schönbrodt and Gerstenberg (2012) was used to mask questions in regards to the three motives of interest, as a way to promote scientific validity. The questionnaire consisted of twenty items, fairly assigned to each motive. The Likert scale used for achievement and affiliation as social motives was identical to the DoPL motive questionnaire. Responses were removed from subsequent statistical analyses, as they were not significant for the current study.

Moreover, SDO was measured with the SDO₆ scale obtained from Sidanius and Pratto (1999). The SDO₆ scale was found to have an α -value of 0.82. Subjects demonstrated their agreement with six statements (e.g. “To get ahead in life, it is sometimes okay to step on other groups.”) rated on a seven-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 7= Strongly Agree). The SDO items were summed and averaged, with higher scores on the SDO₆ scale implying a stronger tendency to accept the current status quo.

Benevolent ($\alpha = 0.79$) and hostile sexism ($\alpha = 0.87$) were measured with the use of Glick and Fiske’s Ambivalent Sexism questionnaire (1996), which was later shortened to a ten-item scale by Sibley (2014). There were five statements for benevolent sexism (e.g. “Women should be cherished and protected by men”) and five items for hostile sexism (e.g. “Women are too easily offended”) for which participants stated their agreement on a six-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 6= Strongly Agree). Greater agreement with the ten statements signals the adoption of sexist beliefs and attitudes.

Finally, feminist identity was evaluated with a single item social identification measure (SISI) within the Feminist Self-identification scale (“I identify as a feminist”; Radke et al, 2018). The validity of single-item scales for identifying with a category or group has already been established across different samples (Postmes, Haslam & Jans, 2013). Participants

signalled their agreement with the single item on a seven-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 7= Strongly Agree).

Procedure:

Participants reviewed the study information sheet, in which the nature of our research and what was required from them, as well as their rights were explained, prior to giving their participation consent. Demographic questions followed, before participants could start completing the survey. Those questions involved their age, gender and SES (employment status and level of education). They were then asked to indicate their level of agreement or degree of importance in regards to a number of short statements. There were six questionnaire sections, which measured benevolent and hostile sexism, feminist identification, SDO, participants' willingness to engage in feminist and protective action, achievement and affiliation motives as well as their goals and how driven they consider themselves to be by dominance, leadership and prestige. Questionnaire sections were displayed in a random order for each participation to minimise order effects. Our target sample was set according to the study's funding limits and sampling lasted for a day, until our target sample was reached.

Statistical Analysis Plan:

All items measured in the survey were summed to create a single score for each of the final variables. We, then, standardised all continuous variables, while gender was dummy coded with Male being the reference level. Subsequently, we computed zero-order correlations and multilevel multivariate multiple regression models, within the frame of Bayesian. Zero-order correlations were computed to test the concurrence between one's engagement in collective action for gender equality and DoPL motives, as well as various attitudes. Bayesian multivariate multiple regression modelling established the predictors of feminist and protective action.

Posterior distributions of regression parameters were based on the findings of previous work (<https://osf.io/3zb6m>). Moreover, the effect size uncertainty was calculated as 95% highest density intervals (HDIs). Regression models were sampled with 6000 iterations. The three power motives were entered into the model as the main predictors, whereas SDO, feminist identity, gender, benevolent and hostile sexism were controlled for. The location of the two samples (UK/US) was modelled with random intercept. Three items from the SDO₆ scale (Sidanius & Pratto, 1999) and one item measuring desire for leadership from the DoPL questionnaire (Suessenbach et al, 2019) were reverse coded prior to any subsequent statistical analyses.

Results:

Descriptive statistics:

Participants scored higher than average for all three social power motives with prestige being the most desirable power strategy. Moreover, they were more willing to engage in feminist rather than protective action. The mean score for feminist identity suggests that our sample has a higher-than-average feminist consciousness. Table 2 displays summarized descriptive statistics for the three social power motives of interest, as well as the study's depended and control variables in their non-standardized scales of measurement.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean (SD)	Median	Range	Min	Max
Leadership motive	13.9 (4.49)	14	20	4	24
Dominance Motive	9.27 (3.72)	9	17	4	21
Prestige Motive	14.63 (3.96)	15	17	4	24
SDO	2.12 (0.98)	2	4.5	1	5.5
FI	4.32 (1.87)	4	6	1	7
Benevolent Sexism	18.37 (6.22)	19	27	5	32
Hostile Sexism	13.81 (6.32)	14	25	5	30
Protective Action	14.10 (4.33)	14	18	3	21
Feminist Action	21.50 (4.96)	22	22	6	28

Zero-order Correlations:

Table 3 shows Bayesian Pearson's zero order correlations. As expected, there was a fair correlation between the two types of collective action for women's rights ($r_{PAFA} = 0.37$, 95% HDI = [0.27, 0.48]). Moreover, willingness to participate in feminist action was weakly correlated with both desire for leadership ($r_{LFA} = 0.12$, 95% HDI = [0.02, 0.22]) and prestige ($r_{PFA} = 0.24$, 95% HDI = [0.12, 0.36]), while there was no evidence of an association with dominance. There was no substantive relationship found between protective action and desire for prestige or leadership, whereas there was a fair correlation between this type of action and the dominance motive ($r_{DPA} = 0.22$, 95% HDI = [0.09, 0.32]). The three motives were weakly correlated with each other, which indicates a tendency to cooccur. Moreover, all DoPL motives are linked to benevolent sexism ($r_{BenSexismP} = 0.13$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.25], $r_{BenSexismD} = 0.26$, 95% HDI = [0.15, 0.38], $r_{BenSexismL} = 0.13$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.25]), with desire for dominance having the strongest relationship with this attitude. This motive was, also, found to be the only one associated to hostile sexism ($r_{HostSexismD} = 0.33$, 95% HDI = [0.22, 0.43]). In addition, prestige ($r_{FemaleP} = 0.18$, 95% HDI = [0.07, 0.30]) and dominance ($r_{FemaleD} = -0.14$, 95% HDI = [-0.26, -0.02]) are respectively positively and negatively associated with identifying as a female, meaning that women are more prestige-motivated and less dominance-motivated compared to men. Prestige was the only power motive to have a substantive correlation with feminist attitudes, which parallels the tendency of prestige-driven individuals to claim moral standards (Suessenbach et al, 2019).

Hostile sexism was found to be negatively correlated with feminist action ($r_{HostSexismFA} = -0.41$, 95% HDI = [-0.61, -0.47]), while no meaningful relationship was there for protective action. These findings suggest that individuals with greater endorsement of hostile sexism are less willing to engage in feminist action, whereas participation in protective action movements is unrelated to this attitude. Benevolent sexism had no relationship with feminist action credibly

different from zero, although this was not the case for its relation to protective action ($r_{BenSexismPA} = 0.19$, 95% HDI = [0.07, 0.31]). This finding was expected, since it is proven that individuals with benevolent sexism views are mainly found to engage in protective action because of their paternalistic mindset and their false beliefs that women should be protected (Estevan-Reina et al, 2020). Furthermore, our findings suggest a cooccurrence between benevolent and hostile sexism views, since there was a moderate correlation between the two ($r = 0.39$, 95% HDI = [0.29, 0.49]). Finally, both types of sexism had a negative relationship with identifying as a female ($r_{BenSexism} = -0.16$, 95% HDI = [-0.27, -0.03], $r_{HostSexism} = -0.33$, 95% HDI = [-0.45, -0.23]).

SDO has a meaningful positive relationship with sexist attitudes ($r_{HostSexismSDO} = 0.50$, 95% HDI = [0.40, 0.59], $r_{BenSexismSDO} = 0.18$, 95% HDI = [0.06, 0.30]). Additionally, SDO views are moderately correlated with feminist action ($r = -0.46$, 95% HDI = [-0.54, -0.34]) and have no meaningful relationship with protective action. This signifies that the higher an individual scores on SDO, the less likely they are to act for real change. SDO is, also, negatively associated with feminist identity ($r = -0.42$, 95% HDI = [-0.52, -0.32]).

Results suggest that protective ($r_{FIPA} = 0.22$, 95% HDI = [0.10, 0.34]) and feminist action ($r_{FIFA} = 0.59$, 95% HDI = [0.51, 0.65]) relate to feminist identity, with the relationship between feminist consciousness and the latter type of action being the strongest of the two. This is, also, the case with their connection to being a woman ($r_{FemaleFA} = 0.13$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.25], $r_{FemalePA} = 0.13$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.25]). As expected, women are more probable to identify as feminists compared to men ($r = 0.40$, 95% HDI = [0.30, 0.51]). Finally, age is negatively correlated with all three DoPL motives and both types of collective action, which suggests a link between aging and loss of motivation.

Table 3: Bayesian Pearson's zero-order correlations and their 95% HDIs between variables of interest.

	FA	PA	Leadership	Dominance	Prestige	Benevolent sexism	Hostile sexism	SDO	FI	Age	Sex
<i>FA</i>	1	0.37** * [0.27, 0.48]	0.12* [0.02, 0.22]	0.05 [-0.08, 0.17]	0.24** [0.12, 0.36]	-0.002 [-0.12, 0.12]	- 0.41*** [-0.51, -0.31]	- 0.46*** [-0.54, -0.34]	0.59*** [0.51, 0.65]	-0.13** [-0.25, -0.01]	0.24*** [0.11, 0.35]
<i>PA</i>		1	0.03 [-0.09, 0.15]	0.22*** [0.09, 0.32]	-0.02 [-0.14, 0.11]	0.19** [0.07, 0.31]	-0.01 [-0.13, 0.11]	-0.02 [-0.15, 0.09]	0.22*** [0.10, 0.34]	-0.18* [-0.29, -0.01]	0.13* [0.01, 0.25]
<i>Leadership</i>			1	0.28*** [0.17, 0.99]	0.41*** [0.30, 0.50]	0.13* [0.01, 0.25]	0.07 [-0.05, 0.20]	0.02 [-0.10, 0.14]	0.10 [-0.02, 0.23]	-0.19** [-0.31, -0.07]	-0.06 [-0.18, 0.07]
<i>Dominance</i>				1	0.26*** [0.14, 0.37]	0.26*** [0.15, 0.38]	0.33*** [0.22, 0.44]	0.22*** [0.10, 0.33]	0.004 [-0.12, 0.12]	-0.28*** [-0.40, -0.16]	-0.14* [- 0.26, - 0.02]
<i>Prestige</i>					1	0.13* [0.01, 0.25]	-0.02 [-0.14, 0.10]	-0.11 [-0.23, 0.01]	0.22*** [0.09, 0.33]	-0.30*** [-0.41, -0.19]	0.18** [0.07, 0.30]
<i>Benevolent sexism</i>						1	0.39*** [0.29, 0.49]	0.18** [0.06, 0.30]	-0.12 [-0.24, 0.00]	-0.07 [-0.18, 0.06]	-0.16** [-0.27, - 0.03]
<i>Hostile sexism</i>							1	0.50*** [0.40, 0.59]	-0.44*** [-0.54, - 0.34]	-0.06 [-0.19, 0.06]	-0.33*** [-0.45, -0.23]
<i>SDO</i>								1	-0.42*** [-0.52, -0.32]	0.05 [-0.07, 0.17]	-0.15** [-0.28, -0.04]
<i>FI</i>									1	-0.11 [-0.22, 0.02]	0.40*** [0.30, 0.51]
<i>Age</i>										1	-0.03 [- 0.16, 0.10]
<i>Sex</i>											1

Note. Probability of direction (*pd*) represents the portion of the posterior distribution that is of the median's sign (Makowski et al., 2019); *** *pd* > 99.95%, ** *pd* > 99.5%, * *pd* > 97.5%. Sex is a binary variable with Male being the reference level.

Pre-registered analysis:

We modelled multiple responses with a single set of predictor variables. Hence, our pre-registered model concurrently predicted ratings on both protective and feminist action (Table 4).

Feminist Action:

Both desire for prestige ($\beta_{PFA} = 0.16$, 95% HDI = [0.09, 0.23]) and leadership ($\beta_{LFA} = 0.08$, 95% HDI = [0.02, 0.14]) were found to indicate one's intention to participate in feminist action for gender equality, while desire for dominance signalled one's opposition to get involved in

said action ($\beta_{DFA} = -0.07$, 95% HDI = [-0.13, -0.01]). This confirms findings from previous work and supports our hypotheses regarding feminist action for all three DoPL motives. As expected, identifying as a feminist predicted willingness to engage in feminist action ($\beta_{FIFA} = 0.30$, 95% HDI = [0.24, 0.37]), indicating that people who consider themselves to be feminists

Figure 1: Relationship between each of the three DoPL (a, b= Dominance, c, d= Leadership, e, f= Prestige) motives and Feminist and Protective Action.

are more likely to confront sexism for egalitarian rather than paternalistic reasons. Similarly, identifying as a female is a predictor of the intent to take part in the progressive helping of feminist action ($\beta_{FemaleFA} = 0.12$, 95% HDI = [0.01, 0.23]). This finding validates that members of disadvantaged groups are more likely to engage in prosocial behaviour for the benefit of their group (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; van Zomeren, Postmes & Spears, 2008). Moreover, greater endorsement of hostile sexism was found to predict low support in feminist action movements ($\beta_{HostSexismFA} = -0.18$, 95% HDI = [-0.24, -0.11]), similarly to high scores on SDO ($\beta_{SDOFA} = -0.33$, 95% HDI = [-0.39, -0.26]). This shows that individuals who hold hostile sexism views and/or accept social inequalities are opposed to feminist action movements. On the contrary,

beliefs that coincide with benevolent sexism were found to indicate willingness to participate in this type of movements ($\beta_{BenSexismFA} = 0.20$, 95% HDI = [0.14, 0.26]).

Table 4: Full summary of Bayesian regression fixed effects coefficients of pre-registered model.

	Feminist Action	Protective Action
	Mean [95% HDI]	Mean [95% HDI]
Intercept	-0.23 [-1.74, 1.29]	-0.47 [-2.58, 1.43]
Feminist Identity	0.30 [0.24, 0.37]	0.14 [0.05, 0.22]
Dominance Motive	-0.07 [-0.13, -0.01]	-0.05 [-0.13, 0.02]
Prestige Motive	0.16 [0.09, 0.23]	0.06 [-0.01, 0.14]
Leadership Motive	0.08 [0.02, 0.14]	-0.03 [-0.11, 0.04]
SDO	-0.33 [-0.39, -0.26]	-0.08 [-0.15, 0.00]
Benevolent Sexism	0.20 [0.14, 0.26]	0.34 [0.27, 0.42]
Hostile Sexism	-0.18 [-0.24, -0.11]	-0.06 [-0.15, 0.02]
Sex	0.16 [0.06, 0.26]	0.29 [0.14, 0.45]

Note. Sex is a binary variable with Male being the reference level. Bold emphasises $0 \notin$ 95% HDI.

Protective Action:

None of the three DoPL motives were found to have a meaningful effect on protective action, which entails that the intent to protect women from gender violence does not depend on power strategies. Results show that feminist identification is a predictor of protective action ($\beta_{FIPA} = 0.14$, 95% HDI = [0.05, 0.22]). Moreover, the effect of identifying as a woman on one's intent to engage in protective action was credibly different from zero ($\beta_{FemalePA} = 0.29$, 95% HDI = [0.14, 0.45]), which is in line with our hypothesis that women will be more involved in all types of collective action for women's rights compared to men. It was shown that benevolent sexism is a strong predictor of taking action to protect women from the consequences of gender inequality ($\beta_{BenSexismPA} = 0.34$ 95% HDI = [0.27, 0.42]), while, on the contrary, high scores on SDO ($\beta_{SDOPA} = -0.08$, 95% HDI = [-0.15, 0.00]) signified one's opposition to participating in protective action.

Exploratory analyses:

We compared multiple expanded versions of our pre-registered model guided by a number of investigative plots. We assumed that the effect of DoPL motives on collective action depends on gender, therefore relevant investigative plots were produced. It was shown that a meaningful interaction between gender and desire for dominance, as well as leadership might be present (see Appendix F). We calculated the expected log pointwise predictive density of the planned and the two exploratory models with the use of Bayesian leave-one-out cross validation ($ELPD_{LOO}$). We assume that a difference in $ELPD$ is meaningful, whenever it is two standard deviations larger than zero (Sebald et al, 2019). Moreover, Bayes factors (BFs) were computed to compare the weight of evidence for one model over the other, whilst adopting a slightly more conservative BF interpretation (Raftery, 1995). There was weak evidence in favour of both exploratory models (see Appendix G). On the contrary, $ELPD_{LOO}$ indicated no substantive evidence that our exploratory models were more fitting than our planned one. The best exploratory model, according to BFs, consisted of the main variables of the planned model and two interactions: the interaction of gender and dominance, as well as gender and leadership. All DoPL motives and control variables remained predictive of feminist action in both exploratory models. Full summary of the models' Bayesian regression fixed effects coefficients can be found in Appendix E.

Discussion:

In the present paper, we aimed to understand the reasons why gender equality is often faced with stalling and reversion of any advances by investigating the power motives behind one's willingness to engage in collective action for the improvement of women's status. It was demonstrated that the three motives derived from Suessenbach and colleagues (2019) taxonomy of social power are reliable and distinct predictors of feminist collective action for women's rights. Moreover, it was confirmed that there are two distinct categories of behaviour

in regards to acting on behalf of women (Radke et al, 2018), since each type of action was differentially predicted. In line with previous papers (Radke et al, 2018), the intent to participate in protective action was more nuanced and less consistent than feminist action.

In agreement with our hypotheses, all DoPL motives were predictive of feminist action. Specifically, individuals who desire leadership and prestige are willing to act for real progress regarding women's rights. This confirms findings from previous work proposing that prestige-oriented individuals tend to demonstrate prosocial behaviour (Suessenbach et al, 2019), while leadership-oriented people are inclined to exhibit helping behaviours, as a way to increase their social status (Van Vungt, 2006). The fact that dominance-motivated individuals do not support feminist action movements, in addition to the positive relationship found between dominance and SDO, confirms their preference for social hierarchy and the existence of submissive and domineering groups. Contrary to our beliefs, none of the social power motives had a meaningful effect on protective action. This entails that people who desire power do not necessarily engage in action with the aim to protect women from violence. Moreover, the positive correlation between all three power motives indicates that the strategic use of one is contingent to the use of the other. A cooccurrence of the three would be sensible, since they share in common the desire for a high rank (Maner & Mead, 2010). Finally, the evidence found in favour of the best-fitting exploratory model, which includes the interaction of gender and dominance, as well as gender and leadership, suggests that the way leadership- and dominance-driven individuals act for women's rights depends on their gender.

Identifying as a female has been shown to be a predictor of both types of collective action for women's rights. This adds to the literature that identifying as a disadvantaged group member motivates them to engage in collective action to improve their status (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; van Zomeren et al, 2008; Radke et al, 2018). Interestingly, identifying as a woman is a stronger predictor for the willingness to participate in protective rather than feminist action.

We hypothesize that this is the case because measures regarding protective action can be perceived as more drastic than feminist action. Groups that are under threat or fear are more likely to support drastic measures, even if they turn out to be less effective (Deflem & McDonough, 2015). As of today, women are intimidated by sexual terrorism and overt violence. Therefore, they would be more supportive of seemingly more extreme movements, as a way to ease their feelings of unsettlement. This implication is worthy of investigating in the future.

Results indicating that protective action and benevolent sexism cooccur signifies the importance of perceiving and confronting sexism, even when it appears in a positive tone, since it can minimise the autonomy of women. Becker and Swim (2012) found that the endorsement of benevolent sexism and the consequences of holding these beliefs could be overcome by providing information about their harmful effects and persuasiveness. Benevolent sexism is, also, a predictor of feminist action, which raises several interesting questions. Future studies are encouraged to study whether individuals who hold benevolent sexism beliefs always undermine women or whether this depends on the context, as a way to better identify and tackle its negative effects.

In addition, results indicated that individuals who endorse hostile sexism oppose feminist action, which confirms that sexism and the perception of women as inferior lie at the root of gender inequality. Finally, according to Radke, Hornsey and Barlow (2016) another way to overcome barriers in the fight for gender equality is to encourage feminist identity. Our findings support this proposal, since it was proven that feminist identity predicts both types of collective action. High feminist consciousness is a stronger predictor for feminist action rather than protective, which gives insight to how one defines a feminist and the purpose of feminism.

Limitations and Future Directions:

The main limitation in studies investigating one's morality and political correctness is social desirability bias. In this situation, responders may demonstrate attitudes society expects them to, instead of choosing an option that represents their true feelings (Grimm, 2010). Although responses were anonymized and questions regarding DoPL motives have been masked by being randomized with questions from Schönbrodt and Gerstenberg's (2012) Achievement and Affiliation questionnaire, the tendency to respond in a way that might not be representative, but rather socially acceptable is still to be expected. Social desirability bias is especially expected from questions concerning dominance, collective action and sexism. Self-report methods allow for social desirability bias to occur, since participants' responses are a product of introspection that does not necessarily signify actual attitudes. This issue has already been raised by Suessenbach and colleagues (2019), which demonstrated that although prestige-motivated people claim to be moral, they do not follow through their claims with actions. Although, leadership- and prestige-driven individuals are willing to engage in feminist action movements and support the cause, they may, eventually not participate in any movements regarding gender equality in real life. An observational study complimentary to ours would be able to segregate biased responses from truly representative attitudes and concurrently evaluate that the three social power motives investigated truly influence the fight for gender equality and the extent of their influence. Actions will always be more reliable than words and claims.

Sample selection bias should, also, be acknowledged as participants choose whether or not to participate in this project. The decision to take part in a study posted in an online platform depends, among others, on how rewarding and long the study will be, as well as whether participants are interested in the study's theme. This makes our sample less representative than we would have liked. We assume that a non-random sample of the population in the UK and US, would not have scored as high on the feminist identity scale or be as willing to engage in

collective action, especially feminist. At this point it should be mentioned, that measures have been taken to tackle this limitation, such as the equal distribution of our study to both males and females. Furthermore, our sample was balanced across the US and UK to ensure that results are representative for both populations. Time limits were imposed and responses were checked for satisficing, as a way to ensure their quality.

Conclusion:

To summarize, we studied the effect of the three social power motives on collective action for women's rights, that being either protective or feminist, whilst controlling for a number of attitudes. By conducting this study, we attempted to predict how leading figures behave regarding movements for gender equality, according to their social power strategy. We proved that leadership and prestige predict feminist action, whereas dominance opposes any attempts for real progress and obstructs the fight for gender equality. In addition, we failed to present evidence that DoPL motives are able to predict protective action. Attitudes, such as benevolent sexism, feminist identity and identifying as a woman are indicators of taking feminist, as well as protective action. On the opposite, hostile sexism beliefs and high scores on SDO demonstrate low support for feminist action, while SDO is, also, a predictor of disagreement with actions to protect women from gender violence. Future observational studies should confirm that leadership- and prestige-driven individuals who support feminist collective action truly engage in it.

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Appendix A – Questionnaire

DoPL survey (US, UK)

Consent You **MUST** be over the age of 18 and living in the US in order to participate in this study.

Study Title: Attitudes toward equality movements

Nature of the study:

You are being asked to take part in a study investigating the relationship between certain personal motivations and attitudes and engagement in certain types of collective action in support of women.

This research is being conducted as part of a Masters thesis project. This anonymous study is being conducted by Maria Kyriakou, Eleanor Holman, and Angelica Gaggioli under the supervision of Dr. Adam Moore (amoore23@ed.ac.uk).

In this study, you will complete an online questionnaire. You will be asked to give your level of agreement or degree of importance of each in a list of short statements. There are no incorrect answers, we are purely interested in your opinion. Please give your answers sincerely as this will help guarantee the success of this study.

Time Commitment:

This study typically takes 10-15 minutes to complete.

Risks and benefits:

There are no known risks to participation in this study. Upon completion of the study, you will be reimbursed £2.35 for your participation.

Confidentiality and use of data:

All the information we collect during the course of the research will be processed in accordance with Data Protection Law. The data will be treated anonymously and will not be linked to any demographic information you may have been asked to provide. Your data will only be referred to by a unique participant number. The anonymous data collected during this study will be used for research purposes and may be shared with other researchers. Results could be used for possible publication and/or conference presentation.

What are my data protection rights?

The University of Edinburgh is a Data Controller for the information you provide. You have the right to access information held about you. Your right of access can be exercised in accordance with Data Protection Law. You also have other rights including rights of correction, erasure and objection. For more details please visit www.ico.org.uk. Questions, comments and requests about your personal data can also be sent to the University Data

Protection Officer at **dpo@ed.ac.uk**.

Voluntary participation and right to withdraw:

Your participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw from the study at any time while you are completing it. You have the right to ask that any data you have supplied be withdrawn/destroyed. You may do so by contacting the researchers.

Further Information:

If you have any questions about what you have just read, please feel free to ask or contact us later. You can contact any one of the researchers by email: amoore23@exseed.ed.ac.uk, m.kyriakou@sms.ed.ac.uk, s1632751@ed.ac.uk, a.gaggioli@sms.ed.ac.uk.

This project has been approved by the PPLS Ethics committee. If you have questions or comments regarding your rights as a participant, they can be contacted at 0131 650 4020 or ppls.ethics@ed.ac.uk

By clicking through to the next page, you consent to the following:

1. **I agree to participate in this study.**
2. I confirm that I have read and understood **how my data will be stored and used.**
3. I understand that I have the **right to terminate this session** at any point.

If you consent, please click the arrow below to begin the questionnaire.

Dem1 What is your age?

▼ 18 (1) ... 85 (68)

Dem2 What is your sex?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Nonbinary (3)
- Prefer not to say (4)

Dem3 What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? *If currently enrolled, highest degree received.*

- Primary School (1)
- GCSEs or National 4-5 or equivalent (2)
- A-levels or Highers or equivalent (3)
- Trade/technical/vocational training (4)
- University undergraduate programme (5)
- University postgraduate programme (6)

Dem4 What best describes your employment status?

- Employed for wages (1)
- Self-employed (2)
- Out of work and looking for work (3)
- Out of work but not currently looking for work (4)
- A homemaker (5)
- A student (6)
- Retired (7)
- Unable to work (8)

ID What is your Prolific ID? Please note that this response should auto-fill with the correct ID.

FI I identify as a feminist

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Rather agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

SDO Please indicate how strongly you disagree or agree with each statement on the scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree):

SDO1 It is OK if some groups have more of a chance in life than others

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

SDO2 Inferior groups should stay in their place

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

SDO3 To get ahead in life, it is sometimes okay to step on other groups

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

SDO4 We should have increased social equality

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

SDO5 It would be good if groups could be equal

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

SDO6 We should do what we can to equalise conditions for different groups

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

SAS Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement using the following scale: 1 = disagree strongly, 2 = disagree somewhat, 3 = disagree slightly, 4 = agree slightly, 5 = agree somewhat, 6 = agree strongly

BS1 Women, compared to men, tend to have a greater moral sensibility

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

BS2 Many women have a quality of purity that few men possess

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

BS3 Women, as compared to men, tend to have a more refined sense of culture and good taste

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

BS4 Women should be cherished and protected by men

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

BS5 Every man ought to have a woman whom he adores

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

HS1 Women are too easily offended

- Strongly disagree (1) (1)
- (2) (2)
- (3) (3)
- (4) (4)
- (5) (5)
- (6) (6)
- Strongly agree (7) (7)

HS2 Women exaggerate problems they have at work

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

HS3 Women seek to gain power by getting control over men

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

HS4 Once a woman gets a man to commit to her she usually tries to put him on a tight leash

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

HS5 When women lose to men in a fair competition, they typically complain about being discriminated against

Strongly disagree (1) (1)

(2) (2)

(3) (3)

(4) (4)

(5) (5)

(6) (6)

Strongly agree (7) (7)

DoPL-A&A The following questionnaire items represent statements or goals. Please rate each statement on a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree, and each goal on a scale of not important to me to extremely important to me.

L1 I relish opportunities in which I can lead others

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

D1 I enjoy bending others to my will

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

D2 I am willing to use aggressive tactics to get my way

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

L2 I have little interest in leading others

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

P1 I feel sad if nobody recognises my unique talents and abilities

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Strongly agree (6)
-

D3 When people challenge me I want to put them down hard

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

D4 I want to twist others around my little finger

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

L3 I feel confident when directing the activities of others

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

P2 I am happy when I can present my achievements to others

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

L4 I make a good leader

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

P3 Recognition from others

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

P4 Be respected and admired by other people

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach1 I am attracted to situations that allow me to test my abilities

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Ach2 My goal is to do at least a little bit more than anyone else has done before

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff1 I try to be in the company of friends as much as possible

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff2 I spend a lot of time visiting friends

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff3 Encounters with other people make me happy

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Strongly agree (6)
-

Aff4 Often I would rather be alone than with a group of friends

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff5 I go out of my way to meet people

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff6 I choose hobbies that I can share with other people

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff7 I like to make as many friends as I can

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Aff8 I feel a rush of energy when I get to know new people

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Rather agree (4)
- Agree (5)
- Strongly agree (6)

Ach3 Maintaining high standards for the quality of my work

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach4 Personally producing work of high quality

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach5 Projects that challenge me to the limits of my ability

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach6 Continuously improve myself

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach7 Continuously engage in new, exciting and challenging goals and projects

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach8 Opportunities to take on more difficult and challenging goals and responsibilities

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach9 Personally doing things better than they have been done before

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Ach10 Opportunities to create new things

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Aff9 Engage in a lot of activities with other people

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

Aff10 Have a wide circle of friends

- Not important to me (1)
- Of little importance to me (2)
- Of some importance to me (3)
- Important to me (4)
- Very important to me (5)
- Extremely important to me (6)

FA-PA Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree):

FA1 I would be willing to challenge sexism when I see it

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

FA2 I would be willing to protest against sexism

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

FA3 I would be willing to boycott companies that do not support women's rights

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

FA4 I would be willing to sign petitions aimed at overcoming sexism

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

US VERSION:

PA1 I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can obtain a gun license and firearm to protect themselves.

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

PA2 I would be willing to sponsor women to attend a self-defense class to learn how to protect themselves.

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly Agree (7)

PA3 I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can be given and trained to use a Taser to protect themselves.

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)

- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

UK VERSION:

PA1 I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can be given and trained to use a legal 3-inch folding blade to protect themselves

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

PA2 I would be willing to sponsor women to attend a self-defense class to learn how to protect themselves

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly Agree (7)

PA3 I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can obtain and be trained to use a legal defense spray to protect themselves

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Slightly disagree (3)
- Neither agree nor disagree (4)
- Slightly agree (5)
- Agree (6)
- Strongly agree (7)

Debrief Thank you for your participation in our study! Your time and effort are greatly appreciated. US VERSION

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

We previously informed you that the purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between personal motivations and certain types of collective action. To provide you with more detail, the goal of our research is to investigate whether social power motives (Suessenbach et al., 2019) predict types of helping behaviour toward women in collective action situations.

Specifically, these helping behaviours take the form of feminist action or protective action. Feminist action is "**action that aims to challenge gender inequality**", such as attending a march or signing a petition. Protective action is "**action that aims to protect women from violence which occurs as a symptom of gender inequality - for example, sponsoring a woman to attend a self-defense class**" (Radke et al., 2018).

Motivation for social power may be categorised into three types: dominance, leadership and prestige (Suessenbach et al., 2019). These differ with respect to the ways people may obtain power in society and the behaviours they are likely to engage in in order to do so.

A fundamental part of gender inequality is the imbalance of power between men and women. For this reason, we predict that, depending on one's type of motivation for social power, people will be more or less willing to engage in actions that seek to change or maintain the status quo (feminist and protective action). Our findings will help us explore the driving forces behind people's involvement in such activities.

In the questionnaire, we also investigated sexist attitudes, attitudes towards general social hierarchies and feminist identification, as we believe these components may have

an effect on the main relationship we are studying.

Confidentiality/Anonymity:

All the information we collected during the course of the research will be processed in accordance with Data Protection Law. The data will be treated anonymously and will not be linked to any demographic information you may have been asked to provide. Your data will only be referred to by a unique participant number. The anonymous data collected during this study will be used for research purposes and may be shared with other researchers. Results could be used for possible publications and/or conference presentation.

Withdrawal of Response:

You have the right to ask that any data you have supplied be withdrawn/destroyed. If you would like to do so, please make a note of the date and time you completed the survey and contact one of the researchers below as soon as possible.

Useful Contact Information:

If you have any questions or concerns regarding this study, its purpose or procedures, or if you have a research-related problem, please feel free to contact the researchers: amoore23@exseed.ed.ac.uk, m.kyriakou@sms.ed.ac.uk, s1632751@ed.ac.uk, a.gaggioli@sms.ed.ac.uk.

Who to contact about your rights as a research participant in the study:

This project has been approved by PPLS Ethics committee. If you have any further questions or comments regarding your rights as a participant, the committee can be contacted at 0131 650 4020 or ppls.ethics@ed.ac.uk.

Further Reading:

Radke, H. R. M., Hornsey, M. J., & Barlow, F. K. (2018). Changing versus protecting the status quo: Why men and women engage in different types of action on behalf of women. *Sex Roles*, 79(9-10), 505-518. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-017-0884-2>

Suessenbach, F., Loughnan, S., Schönbrodt, F. D., & Moore, A. B. (2019). The dominance, prestige, and leadership account of social power motives. *European Journal of Personality*, 33(1), 7-33. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2184>

Appendix B – Scales used

Feminist/protective action questionnaire

Radke, H. R. M., Hornsey, M. J., & Barlow, F. K. (2018). Changing versus protecting the status quo: Why men and women engage in different types of action on behalf of women. *Sex Roles, 79*, 505-518.

Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement on a scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*):

1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *rather disagree*, 4 = *neither agree nor disagree*, 5 = *slightly agree*, 6 = *agree*, 7 = *strongly agree*

I would be willing to challenge sexism when I see it.	
I would be willing to protest against sexism.	
I would be willing to boycott companies that do not support women’s rights.	
I would be willing to sign petitions aimed at overcoming sexism.	
I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can be given and trained to use a legal 3-inch folding blade to protect themselves.	
I would be willing to sponsor women to attend a self-defense class to learn how to protect themselves.	
I would be willing to sponsor women so that they can obtain and be trained to use a legal defense spray to protect themselves.	

DoPL Questionnaire (12-item questionnaire with 4-item scales)

Suessenbach, F., Loughnan, S., Schonbrodt, F. D., Moore, A. B., & Back, M. (2019). The Dominance, Prestige, and Leadership Account of Social Power Motives. *European Journal of Personality, 33*(1), 7-33.

The following questionnaire items represent **statements**. Please indicate on a scale from 1 = strongly disagree to 6 = strongly agree how much you agree or disagree with each item.

1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *somewhat disagree*, 4 = *somewhat agree*, 5 = *agree*, 6 = *strongly agree*

I relish opportunities in which I can lead others.	
I enjoy bending others to my will.	
I am willing to use aggressive tactics to get my way.	
I have little interest in leading others.	
I feel sad if nobody recognises my unique talents and abilities.	
When people challenge me I want to put them down hard.	
I want to twist others around my little finger.	
I feel confident when directing the activities of others.	
I am happy when I can present my achievements to others.	
I make a good leader.	

The following questionnaire items represent **goals**. Please indicate on a scale from 1 = Not important to me to 6 = extremely important how important these goals are for you.

1 = not important to me, 2 = of little importance to me, 3 = of some importance to me, 4 = important to me, 5 = very important to me, 6 = extremely important to me

Recognition from others.	
Be respected and admired by other people.	

Achievement & Affiliation Motive Questionnaire (used to mask DoPL questions)

Schönbrodt, F. D., & Gerstenberg, F. X. R. (2012). An IRT analysis of motive questionnaires: The unified motive scales. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 46, 725–742

Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement using the following scale:

1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *slightly disagree*, 4 = *slightly agree*, 5 = *agree*, 6 = *strongly agree*

Achievement Motivation:	
I am attracted to situations that allow me to test my abilities	
My goal is to do at least a little bit more than anyone else has done before	
Affiliation Motivation:	
I try to be in the company of friends as much as possible	
I spend a lot of time visiting friends	
Encounters with other people make me happy	
Often I would rather be alone than with a group of friends	
I go out of my way to meet people	
I choose hobbies that I can share with other people	
I like to make as many friends as I can	
I feel a rush of energy when I get to know new people	

Please indicate the degree to which you rate the importance of each goal using the following scale:

1 = *not important to me*, 2 = *of little importance*, 3 = *of some importance to me*, 4 = *important to me*, 5 = *very important to me*, 6 = *extremely important to me*

Achievement Motivation:	
Maintain high standards for the quality of my work	
Personally producing work of high quality	
Projects that challenge me to the limits of my ability	
Continuously improve myself	
Continuously engage in new, exciting and challenging goals and projects	
Opportunities to take on more difficult and challenging goals and responsibilities	
Personally doing things better than they have been done before	
Opportunities to create new things	
Affiliation Motivation:	
Engage in a lot of activities with other people	
Have a wide circle of friends	

Shortened Ambivalent Sexism Inventory

Sibley, C. G. (2014). Archive of NZAVS questionnaires. *NZAVS Technical Documents*, e06.

ORIGINAL SCALE: Glick, P., & Fiske, S. (1996). The Ambivalent Sexism Inventory: Differentiating Hostile and Benevolent Sexism. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 70(3), 491-512.

Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement using the following scale: 1 = *disagree strongly*, 2 = *disagree somewhat*, 3 = *disagree slightly*, 4 = *agree slightly*, 5 = *agree somewhat*, 6 = *agree strongly*

Benevolent Sexism	
Women compared to men, tend to have greater moral sensibility	
Many women have a quality of purity that few men possess	
Women, as compared to men, tend to have a more refined sense of culture and good taste	
Women should be cherished and protected by men	
Every man ought to have a woman whom he adores	
Hostile Sexism	
Women are too easily offended	
Women exaggerate problems they have at work	
Women seek to gain power by getting control over men	
Once a woman gets a man to commit to her she usually tries to put him on a tight leash	
When women lose to men in a fair competition, they typically complain about being discriminated against.	

Shortened Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) Questionnaire

Sibley, C. G. (2014). Archive of NZAVS questionnaires. *NZAVS Technical Documents*, e06.

ORIGINAL SCALE: Sidanius, J., & Pratto, F. (1999). Social dominance: An intergroup theory of social hierarchy and oppression. *Cambridge University Press*.

Please indicate how strongly you disagree or agree with each statement on the scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*):

1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *rather disagree*, 4 = *neither agree nor disagree*, 5 = *slightly agree*, 6 = *agree*, 7 = *strongly agree*

It is OK if some groups have more of a chance in life than others.	
Inferior groups should stay in their place.	
To get ahead in life, it is sometimes okay to step on other groups.	
We should have increased social equality.	
It would be good if groups could be equal.	
We should do what we can to equalise conditions for different groups.	

Feminist Self-Identification (forced-choice measure)

Radke, H. R. M., Hornsey, M. J., & Barlow, F. K. (2018). Changing versus protecting the status quo: Why men and women engage in different types of action on behalf of women. *Sex Roles*, 79, 505-518.

Postmes, T., Haslam, S. A., & Jans, L. (2013). A single-item measure of social identification: Reliability, validity, and utility. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 52, 597–617.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12006>.

Please indicate how strongly you disagree or agree with each statement on the scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*):

1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *rather disagree*, 4 = *neither agree nor disagree*, 5 = *slightly agree*, 6 = *agree*, 7 = *strongly agree*

I identify as a feminist.	
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Appendix C – Employment and educational status of participants

The education level of the majority of participants was postgraduate or undergraduate studies (134, 55.6%; 18, 7.47% A-levels or equivalent; 15, 6.22% GCSE or equivalent; 47, 19.50% Primary School; 18, 7.47% Trade/Technical/Vocational training). In addition, most subjects reported that they are currently out of work with a fair amount of them looking for a job (132, 54.78%) and the rest being retired, students, homemakers, unable to or not interested in working (58, 24.06%). 39 participants reported to be self-employed (16.18%) and 12 were employed for wages (4.98%).

Level of education

Employment status

Appendix D – Summarized regression fixed effects coefficients of Exploratory Models

Model 2 (exploratory):

Full summary of Bayesian regression fixed effects coefficients of Model 2 (exploratory).

	Feminist Action	Protective Action
	Mean [95% HDI]	Mean [95% HDI]
Intercept	-0.32 [-1.99, 1.07]	-0.45 [-2.27, 1.47]
Feminist Identity	0.30 [0.23, 0.36]	0.13 [0.04, 0.22]
Dominance Motive	-0.14 [-0.21, -0.07]	-0.12 [-0.21, -0.01]
Prestige Motive	0.15 [0.09, 0.21]	0.05 [-0.03, 0.04]
Leadership Motive	0.11 [0.03, 0.18]	-0.06 [-0.15, 0.04]
SDO	-0.33 [-0.39, -0.27]	-0.08 [-0.16, -0.00]
Benevolent Sexism	0.19 [0.13, 0.25]	0.33 [0.26, 0.41]
Hostile Sexism	-0.18 [-0.24, -0.11]	-0.08 [-0.17, 0.01]
Sex	0.16 [0.07, 0.26]	0.31 [0.15, 0.46]
D:Sex	0.19 [0.11, 0.27]	0.17 [0.06, 0.28]
L:Sex	-0.08 [-0.16, -0.1]	-0.01 [-0.11, 0.08]
FI:HS	0.00 [-0.09, 0.10]	-0.03 [-0.15, 0.09]

Note. Sex is a binary variable with Male being the reference level. Bold emphasises $0 \notin$ 95% HDI.

Model 3 (exploratory:)

Full summary of Bayesian regression fixed effects coefficients of Model 3 (exploratory).

	Feminist Action	Protective Action
	Mean [95% HDI]	Mean [95% HDI]
Intercept	-0.18 [-1.74, 1.79]	-0.43 [-2.16, 1.40]
Feminist Identity	0.30 [0.24, 0.36]	0.13 [0.04, 0.22]
Dominance Motive	-0.13 [-0.21, -0.06]	-0.12 [-0.21, -0.02]
Prestige Motive	0.16 [0.09, 0.22]	0.05 [-0.03, 0.13]
Leadership Motive	0.11 [0.03, 0.18]	-0.06 [-0.15, 0.03]
SDO	-0.33 [-0.39, -0.27]	-0.08 [-0.16, -0.00]
Benevolent Sexism	0.18 [0.12, 0.25]	0.33 [0.25, 0.41]
Hostile Sexism	-0.19 [-0.25, -0.13]	-0.08 [-0.17, 0.01]
Sex	0.17 [0.07, 0.27]	0.31 [0.15, 0.46]
D:Sex	0.17 [0.09, 0.25]	0.17 [0.06, 0.27]
L:Sex	-0.08 [-0.15, -0.00]	-0.01 [-0.11, 0.08]

Note. Sex is a binary variable with Male being the reference level. Bold emphasises $0 \notin$ 95% HDI.

Appendix E -Checks for planned model

Posterior Predictive Check for standardised Feminist Action (planned model)

Posterior Predictive Check for standardised Protective Action (planned model)

Appendix F – Investigative Plots

The effect of DoPL motives on Collective Action (Feminist, Protective) according to Gender (Male, Female). The effect of DoPL motives on Collective Action (Feminist, Protective) according to

Hostile Sexism beliefs on Collective Action (Feminist and Protective), according to each of the seven responses for Feminist Identity ("Strongly disagree"=1, "Disagree"=2, "Slightly disagree"=3, "Neither agree nor disagree"=4, "Slightly agree"= 5, "Agree"=6, "Strongly Agree"=7). Values are unstandardized.

Benevolent Sexism beliefs on Collective Action (Feminist and Protective), according to each of the seven responses for Feminist Identity (Strongly disagree"=1, "Disagree"=2, "Slightly disagree"=3, "Neither agree nor disagree"=4, "Slightly agree"= 5, "Agree"=6, "Strongly Agree"=7). Values are unstandardized.

Appendix G – Model Comparisons

Model differences in their expected predictive accuracy (elpd_diff) and their standard error.

	elpd_diff	Standard Error (SE)
Model 1 (planned)	-8.3	5.6
Model 2 (exploratory)	0.0 (denominator)	0.0
Model 3 (exploratory)	-3.3	3.7

Bayes Factors for Model Comparison

	BF
Model 1 (planned)	0.0 (denominator)
Model 2 (exploratory)	6.47
Model 3 (exploratory)	4.50